

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№12

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2025-yil, dekabr.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayeich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z. Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golischeva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukxonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA DAVRIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI LIKVIDLILIK XAVFINI BOSHQARISHI.....	44
Baxromov Nodirjon Muxammadamin o'g'li	
TURIZM XIZMATLAR BOZORI ISTE'MOLCHILARINI SEGMENTLASH USULI ASOSIDA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA KONSEPSIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH.....	48
Maxmudova Aziza Pirmamatovna	
“INNOVATSION AGROTEKNOLOGIYALAR VA “YASHIL IQTISODIYOT” TAMOIYILLARI ASOSIDA G'ALLA YETISHTIRISH BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	53
Turayeva Gulizahro	
АНАЛИЗ ЦЕНОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ЗЕРНОВЫЕ ПРОДУКТЫ ПО ДАННЫМ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫМ ИСЛЕДОВАНИЯМ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ НАМАНГАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ).....	57
Бахриддинов Жаҳонгирбек Равшанжон ўғли	
KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJINI TA'MINLASHDA BOZOR INFRATUZILMALARINING AHAMIYATI.....	62
G'aniyev Botir Baxtiyorovich, Zakirova Gulnora Mirzaliyevna	
KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARI FAOLIYATINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASI VA YO'LLARI.....	67
Shodmonqulov Kamoliddin Murodillaevich	
INNOVATION FAOLIYAT XARAJATLARINING BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	73
Mustafoyev Akbar Mustafo o'g'li	
MAHSULOT DIVERSIFIKATSIYASI VA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ASOSIDA EKSPORT POTENSIALINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	78
Maxkamov Ibrayim, Jo'raboyeva Shohida Kamoliddin qizi	
REKLAMA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARI ROLI.....	83
Abduxalilova Laylo To'xtasinovna, Raxmonqulova Shahrizoda	
SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTDA YOPIQ SIKL NAZARIYASINING ROLI.....	87
Sodikov Zokir Rustamovich	
YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHDA MOLIYAVIY RAG'BATLAR VA ULARNING NATIJALARI.....	92
Axmadjonova Gulmira Xabibulla qizi	
MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTI RIVOJLANISHIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING ROLI.....	97
G'aniyev Baydulla Toshmurodovich	
АНАЛИЗ ПОДХОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ БАНКОВ К РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЮ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ БАНКОВСКИХ ПРОДУКТОВ: СРАВНЕНИЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ.....	101
Даулетиярова Шахло	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ЦЕННЫХ БУМАГ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	109
Кадилова Хадича Тураевна	
XORIJ MAMLAKATLARINING IQTISODIYOTNI UGLERODSIZLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI: O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN TAKLIFLAR.....	115
D.X. Pulatov, F.E.Shamsiyev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOM MOLIYASI: MUAMMOLAR VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	125
Sattorov Ixtiyor Ochilovich, Karimov Shohruh Yo'ldoshali o'g'li	
HISOB SIYOSATI TARKIBIY TUZILISHI MASALALARI.....	133
Botirova Raximaxon Abdujabbarovna	
QURILISHDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING MOLIYAVIY TAHLILI.....	136
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	

KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI AHOLI TURMUSH FAROVONLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	144
<i>Axmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI PORTFELI TAHLILI.....	149
<i>Madraximov Ilxom Kamilovich</i>	
FOYDA SOLIG'INING O'ZIGA XOS MUAMMOLI JIHATLARI.....	154
<i>Zaripov Xusan Baxodirovich</i>	
AGRAR SEKTORNI INNOVATSION MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHDA INVESTITSIYA OQIMLARINI BOSHQARISH MODELLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	159
<i>Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MARKETING TADQIQODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	163
<i>Jalilov Jamshid G'anjionovich, Safarov Zavqiddin Zokir o'g'li</i>	
MINTAQA SANOAT TARMOG'I RIVOJLANISHINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI.....	168
<i>Xayitboev Abror Quvondiqovich</i>	
РОЛЬ СМЕШАННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ (BLENDED FINANCE) В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ КОММУНАЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ: УРОКИ РАЗВИВАЮЩИХСЯ СТРАН.....	174
<i>Гулмаматова Дурдона Шерали кизи</i>	
KORXONALARDA STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV.....	180
<i>Musayeva Dilnoza Dilshatovna</i>	
BANK TIZIMIDA MARKETING AHAMIYATI VA BANK MARKETINGI.....	184
<i>Usubjonov Zaxriddin Vasliddin o'g'li</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN XORJIY KREDIT MABLAG'LARINI JALB KILISH HUQUQIY JIHATLARI.....	189
<i>Qulliyev Anvar Zayniddinovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINI TRANSFORMATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA CHAKANA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	194
<i>Alimov Umid O'ktambayevich</i>	
MAHSULOTLARNING RAQAMLI PASPORTI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH OMILLARI VA TO'SIQLARI.....	200
<i>Avloqulova Sadoqat Sobirjon qizi</i>	
KORXONALARDA FOYDA VA ZARARLARNI TAHLIL QILISHDA INNOVATSION METODLAR AHAMIYATI.....	207
<i>Ernazarov Ortiq Eshnazarovich, Farog'at Xo'jabekova</i>	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА НА ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЕ, А ТАКЖЕ НОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ДОХОДОВ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ.....	212
<i>Останов Эгамберди</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA INNOVASION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI INTEGRATSIYALASH: MOHIYATI VA RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	218
<i>Xakimova Xulkar Xamidovna</i>	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON VA XORAZM OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI HAMDA UNI YANADA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	224
<i>Tleuov Niyetulla Raxmanovich</i>	
OILAVIY KORXONALARNING IQTISODIY TIZIMDAGI O'RNI.....	230
<i>Shadiyeva Gulnora Mardiyevna, Rustamova Zarina Rustamovna</i>	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEXANIZMLARI.....	234
<i>Sadikov Shoxrux Shuxratovich</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASI KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI XIZMATLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	238
<i>Asenbaeva Aydaygul Edenbaevna</i>	
BARQARORLIK VA YASHIL MENEJMENT: ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR VA AMALIY AHAMIYATI.....	242
<i>Djalilova Dilbar Abdikarim qizi</i>	

HUDUDLARNING IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI INNAVATSION-INVESTITSION BOSHQARISH STRATEGIYASI VA MEXANIZMI (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	247
Maqsudova Malohatxon Maqsudovna, Yaxshimuratov Maqsadbek Narimon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI DAVLAT BUDJETINI 2026-YILGI SOLIQ SIYOSATINING TAHLILI VA XALQARO SOLISHTIRMA YONDASHUVI	251
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON MINTAQALARIDA AYOLLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI.....	256
Mamataliyeva Dilnoza Raxmonovna	
TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUV SHAROITIDA INVESTITSİYALAR SHAKLLANISHI VA ULARNI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	259
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SAVDO TASHKILOTLARINING FAOLIYATI VA RIVOJLANISH HOLATI.....	264
B. Sulaymonov	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" MODELIGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING IQTISODIY FAOLLIGI.....	270
Xonto'rayev Obbosxon Kamolxon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	274
Xoshimov Pazliddin Zuxurovich	
KICHIK BIZNES ORQALI ISH O'RINLARINI YARATISH STRATEGIYALARI: NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA.....	278
Ergasheva Nigora Abdigapparovna	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'INING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	283
Quryozov Sardorbek Sharifboevich	
РАЗРАБОТКА И ПРИОРИТИЗАЦИЯ КЛЮЧЕВЫХ ИНДИКАТОРОВ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЛЯ ОБЩЕНАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПАНЕЛИ МОНИТОРИНГА ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ БОЛЬНИЦ: ЭКСПЕРТНАЯ ОЦЕНКА СО СТОРОНЫ РУКОВОДИТЕЛЕЙ МЕДУЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ	290
Шухратов Мамуржон Шухрат угли	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYAT ORGANLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR	297
Nurmurodov Zafarjon Nurmurod o'g'li	
BANK TIZIMINING BARQAROR MOLIVAVIY RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH VOSITALARI	303
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	
ЗЕЛЕНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ В ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА.....	308
Халиков С. Х.	
HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA KICHIK BIZNESNI ROLI VA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH CHORALARI.....	313
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ ПРОЦЕСС СТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ФАРМАЦЕВТИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ.....	317
Мажидова Фарангиз Фуркатзода	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDAGI TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	321
Isakov Oybek Jamoliddinovich	
NORASMIY KOOPERATSIYA MUNOSABATLARINING FERMER XO'JALIKLARI YETISHTIRGAN MAHSULOT MIQDORIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH.....	325
Ismoilov Azamat	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA FOIZ RISKINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTI.....	332
Seitnazarov Daniyar Baxadirovich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA SUT VA SUT MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLOVCHI KORXONALAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	341
Normuradov Nurbek Sunatilloevich	
"AYOL RAHBARLAR: RAHBARLIK SALOHİYATI VA ISH JOYIDA TENGLIK" FRANSIYA DAVLATI TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA	346
Abduraxmonova Feruzabonu	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDAGI KLASTERLARNING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH.....	352
Dildora Yuldasheva	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING DEPOZIT BAZASINING YETARLILIGINI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI	359
I.J. Isakov	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH VA IQTISODIY DIAGNOSTIKA O'TKAZISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	363
Xo'jaxonov Ma'rufxon Xamidxonovich, Axmedov Oybek Turg'unpulatovich	
INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNI MOLIYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI YECHISH YO'LLARI.....	369
Egamberdiyeva Dilorom Botir qizi, Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
“KREATIV IQTISODIYOT” HAMDA “TURIZM” TUSHUNCHALARINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	374
Abdurasulov Shovqiddin Erkin o'g'li	
THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY AND DEVELOPMENT FACTORS.....	380
Rakhimov Bakhromjon Ibroximovich	
INVESTITSIYALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	386
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich	
GLOBAL INCOME INEQUALITY IN 2024: CAUSES, PATTERNS, AND CONSEQUENCES.....	393
Ilxomjonov Jaxongir Alisher o'g'li	
ТОРГОВЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ В СВОБОДНО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОНАХ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ	401
Шарифходжаев Шавкат Окилович, Ачилова Ширин Шавкат кизи	
O'ZBEKISTON KON-METALLURGIYA SANOATI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA HOZIRGI HOLATI	407
Ergashov Botirjon Ergashovich	
PENSIYA JAMG'ARMASIDA DAVLAT BUDJETI TRANSFERTLARI ULUSHI HAMDA UNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	415
Sherjonov Doniyor Saparbayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARINI QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORIDAN FOYDALANIB MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI.....	419
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'I BO'YICHA FIRIBGARLIKLAR: MEXANIZMLARI, SABABLARI VA ULARNI OLDINI OLIISH YO'LLARI.....	425
Eshkarayev Bobir Chariyevich	
TOG' VA TOG'OLDI HUDUDLARIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	431
Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna	
TURIZM SOHASINING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI (SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	435
Xalimov Shaxboz Xalimovich	
SANOATDA IQTISODIY MOLIYAVIY HISSOBOTLAR XALQARO STANDARTLARINI RAQOBATBARDOSH KORPORATIV STRATEGIYALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA QO'LLASH.....	442
Turaboev Ibroxim Ismoil o'g'li	
ФОНДИРОВАНИЕ И СТРАХОВАНИЕ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ РИСКАМИ АПК: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ	447
Дурманов Акмал Шаймарданович	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARI RIVOJLANISHINING STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI	456
Atajanova Guli Maxsudbekovna	
JAHON MOLIYAVIY BOZORLARI BARQARORLIGIGA GLOBAL IQTISODIY INQIROZLAR VA GEOSIYOSIY OMILLARNING TA'SIRI HAMDA ULARNI BOSHQARISH STRATEGIYALARI	462
Abdurazakova Nargiza Rixsibayevna	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINING IQTISODIY TAHLILI.....	467
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich	
PAXTA TOZALASH KORXONALARINING TARKIBIY BO'LINMALARIDA MOLIVAVIY BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	474
Murodov Orif Jumayevich, G'ulomov Xaydarbek Ilyos o'g'li	
BARQAROR KELAJAK SARI: MAMLAKATDA EKOLOGIK XAVFSIZLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH	482
Abdullaev Shavkatjon Maxmudillaevich	
ZAMONAVIY IQTISODIY SHAROITLARDI KORXONALARNING MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH	487
Abdulakimova Moxina Farxod qizi	
UMUMIY OVQATLANISH SHAHOBCHALARINING FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	493
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJINI O'RGANISH VA XIZMAT SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI	498
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
MINTAQADA TARIXIY VA MADANIY TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARINI KENGAYTIRISHDA DAVLAT HAMDA XUSUSIY SHERIKCHILIK TIZIMIDAN FOYDALANISH	504
Xusanov Chari Kadirovich	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	509
Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna	
THE IMPACT OF AGRICULTURAL CLUSTERS ON FOOD SECURITY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY	514
Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin ugli	
OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA ISSIQXONA IQTISODIYOTINI O'RNI VA NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLAR	520
Otavullaev Sukhrob Sa'dullo o'g'li	
IJTIMOY AHAMIYATI YUQORI LOYIHALARNI DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGI ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	524
Taspanova Ayzada Kenjebayevna	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA RAQOBAT STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	529
Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna, Jamolova Aziza	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ KORXONALARIDA ISTE'MOLCHILARNING XULQ-ATVORINI O'RGANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	537
Sultonova Zulxumor, Bobojonov Baxrombek Ro'zimovich	
INTERNATIONAL TRADE BETWEEN INTEGRATION AND ISOLATION: INNOVATION AND UNCERTAINTY IN A FRAGMENTING GLOBAL ECONOMY.....	542
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI QO'NG'IROT TUMANIDA SIGIRLAR BOSH SONINING PROGNOZ KO'RSATKICHLARI	548
Sabit Gabbarov	
TO'QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	552
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna, Xo'janova Husnora	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIY O'SISH SIFAT OMILLARINING TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	558
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
ОБЩАЯ КОНЦЕПЦИЯ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РЕСУРСОВ.....	567
Зайналов Джохонгир Расулович	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКОВ КАПИТАЛОВ	571
Хотамкулова Мадина Санжар кизи, Зайналов Джохонгир Расулович	

IPOTEKA KREDITI MEKANIZMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA AMALIY ISHLAR TAHLILI	576
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola Sulaymon qizi	
KORXONALARDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	581
Abdurashidova Nigora Alisherovna, Abduqodirova Donoxon	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI VA MEZONLARI.....	588
Jumanov Ruslanbek Bobojanovich	
O'ZBEKISTONIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI	592
Rasulev Alisher Fayziyevich, Qodirov Asliddinxo'ja Mahammadjon o'g'li	
STUDY OF THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF GREEN BONDS, ECOLOGICAL LOANS, AND GREEN INVESTMENT FUNDS, AS WELL AS THEIR IMPORTANCE IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM.....	595
Avazov Azizbek Ashurali o'g'li	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK TERMINOLOGIYASINING ILMIY-TAHLILIIY TALQINI.....	603
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI.....	608
Rasulev Alisher Fayziyevich, Qodirov Asliddinxo'ja Mahammadjon o'g'li	
FERMER XO'JALIKLARIDA INVESTITSION JARAYONLARNI TASHKIL ETISH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	611
Kdirbaev Amir Marat uli	
ITALIYA VA YAPONIYADA DAVLAT QARZINING UZOQ MUDDATLI BARQARORLIGI: FISKAL QOIDALAR VA QARZ BOSHQARUVI STRATEGIYALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	614
Abdurahimov Abror Zafarovich, L.M. Tashpulatova	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ: ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПЕРСОНАЛИЗАЦИИ, ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ	621
Камалова Малика Низамовна, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNING ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINI IFODALOVCHI ASOSIY OMILLAR	626
Raxmonov Bekzod Sharibjon o'g'li	
GLOBAL XAVFLARNING KESKINLASHUVI SHAROITIDA QAYTA SUG'URTANI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	631
Norov Zarif Shamsiddinovich	
INNOVATSION SUG'URTA XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI IXTIYORIY SUG'URTA XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	638
Xayitov Nodirjon Uzokovich	
VOSITACHILIK XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATUVCHI SUBYEKTLAR AUDITI SIFAT NAZORATI.....	652
O.Q. Qo'shmatov	
AUDITORLIK XULOSASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MATEMATIK MODELLARDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI	657
I.Qo'ziyev, F.Ochilov	
MAJBURIYATLAR HISOBINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	664
Ochilov Farxodjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
ВОПРОСЫ РЕОРГАНИЗАЦИИ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В СЕЛЬКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ	669
Розиков Жалил Жалолович	
TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALAR AUDITINI O'TKAZISH TARTIBI.....	678
M.Xayitboyev	
USTAV KAPITAL HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	683
Inomjon Sherimbetov	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KOOPERATIVLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	688
Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich, Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkobilovich	

EKSPORT BOZORLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHDA MOLIYAVIY RAG‘BATLARNING ROLI	694
Galiyev Tohir Fazliddinovich	
ZAMONAVIY LOGISTIKA TIZIMIDA MARKETING STARTEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	700
Abduqodirova Umida G‘ayrat qizi	
QASHQADARYO URBANIZATSIYALASHGAN HUDUDLARIDA AGLOMERATSIYA JARAYONLARIGA TA‘SIR KO‘RSATUVCHI OMILLAR	706
Nazarova Feruza Usmonovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN ALOQA KORXONALARINI KREDITLASHNING ZARURLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI.....	713
Shaymatov Mansur Jo‘rabaevich	
MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARNI TAN OLISH	720
Odiljonova Oybachin Fayzullo qizi	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA INNOVATSION TRANSFORMATSIYA BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH	724
Sanetullaev Aybek Esbosinovich	
XALQARO AVTOMOBIL ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KOMPANIYALARNING RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	728
Xidoyatov Mirsaid Mirmuhsomovich	
ENSURING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: STRATEGIES FOR RESILIENCE IN AN ERA OF DECLINING RESOURCES AND RISING EXPECTATIONS.....	734
Inomiddin Imomov	
“YASHIL” TEXNOLOGIYALARNI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	744
Miraxmedova Maftuna Ibragimovna	
ИНТЕГРАЛЬНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОЦЕНКЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	751
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
AHOLI DAROMADLARI VA ULARNING SHAKLLANISH MANBALARI.....	756
So‘fiyeva Xusniya Soxibjonovna	
НАУЧНО-МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЮ И РАЗВИТИЮ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	760
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмуханбетовна	
СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПОДХОДОВ ПО ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИОННОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ МАЛОМОЩНЫХ СЕТЕВЫХ ФОТОЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСКИХ СТАНЦИЙ	766
А.Р. Кудратов	
IJTIMOYIY XIZMATLAR KO‘RSATISH JARAYONIDA TASHKILIY VA IQTISODIY MUNOSABATLAR	775
Berdiyeva Nafisa Qahramonovna	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA INNOVATSION BIZNESNI BOSHQARISH VA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ORQALI SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH	780
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o‘g‘li	
GRUZIYA TAJRIBASIDA BARQAROR TURIZMNI TA‘MINLASHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNING O‘ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO‘LLANILISHI.....	786
Suyunova Dilnoza Mexridin qizi	
INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNING MINTAQADA XIZMAT KO‘RSATISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDAGI XUSUSIYATLARI.....	790
Fayziyeva Shirin Shodmonovna	
QORAQALPOG‘ISTON HUDUDIDA ETNOGRAFIK TURIZM KLASTERINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY OMILLARI	795
Kunnazarova Orazxan	
MAMALAKATIMIZ IMPORTI VA EKSPORTIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING ULUSHI	798
Jo‘rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
YEVROOBLIGATSIYA VA UNING AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI TOMONIDAN EMISSIYASI	807
Avezov Ibrohim Ilxomovich	

IQTISODIYOTDAGI INNOVATSION O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI BOSHQARISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	808
<i>Xonkeldiyeva Komilaxon Ravshanjon qizi</i>	
SPORT ANJOMLARI SANOATIDA INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI TIZIMLASHTIRISH MODELINING ZARURATI.....	813
<i>Xamraqulov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES AND THE APPLICATION OF NEUROMARKETING METHODS IN THEIR DEVELOPMENT.....	819
<i>Samadov Asqar Nishonovich, Latipova Go'zal</i>	
OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	825
<i>Mavlanova Barchinoy Shonazar qizi</i>	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA INVESTITSİYALAR AHAMIYATINING EMPERIK TAHLILI	831
<i>Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Najmiddinov Yahyo Fazliddin o'g'li</i>	
YASHIL TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MEHMONXONALAR ROLI: MUAMMOLAR VA IMKONIYATLAR.....	840
<i>Raxmonova Nigina Anvarovna</i>	
IJTIMOY SIYOSAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI: O'ZBEKISTONNING AMALIY YONDASHUVI VA RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	844
<i>Bafoyev Farrux Jo'raqulovich</i>	
AHOLI IJTIMOY HIMOYASINI KUCHAYTIRISH MUAMMOLARI	852
<i>Ulashev Xubbim Askarovich</i>	
YASHIL TA'LIM RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI: YAPONIYA MISOLIDA	856
<i>Raxshona Nabibullayeva</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONING MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA TA'SIRI.....	861
<i>Mo'minov Yahyobek Shokirjon o'g'li</i>	
TUROPERATORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	865
<i>Toshev Akmal Salimovich</i>	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI MINTAQADA AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	874
<i>Quldasheva Maftuna Musurmon qizi</i>	
ФАКТОРЫ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	878
<i>Алиева Эльнара Аметовна, Рахматхонов Саидодилхон Расулхон угли</i>	
МЕХАНИЗМЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ В СТРАНАХ С РАЗВИВАЮЩЕЙСЯ ЭКОНОМИКОЙ: РОЛЬ ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ, ДИНАМИКА РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И МАЛАЙЗИИ.....	884
<i>Нарзуллаева Мехрангиз Ақобировна</i>	
DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLAR SAVDOSIDA QIYMAT ZANJIRI TAHLILI: IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	893
<i>Maftuna Ermatova Arslonbek qizi</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON VA TURKMANISTON O'RTASIDAGI SAVDO AYLANMASI TAHLILI	899
<i>Voxidova Mehri Xasanovna</i>	
GLOBAL KOMPANIYALARDA RAQAMLI MENEJMENTNING SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	905
<i>Axmedov Sardor Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHLARI VA GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK-HUQUQIY TA'LIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	912
<i>Jumanazar Xolmuminov</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING JAHON TAJRIBASI	916
<i>Kalandarova Elnura Muzaffar qizi</i>	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUDUDLARNING INVESTITSİYAVIY JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	921
<i>Rahmatullayev Bobir Chorshamiyevich</i>	

FINANCING WATER RESILIENCE: A FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS OF SOVEREIGN BLUE BOND ISSUANCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....	926
Yakubov Jakhongir	
УКРЕПЛЕНИЕ ПАРТНЁРСТВО И СОЗДАНИЕ ЕДИНСТВЕННОГО ЭНЕРГОРЫНКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	929
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ ЗРЕЛОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ КАК ФАКТОР РОСТА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ: МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ МОДЕЛИ.....	935
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна, Табаков Евгений Сергеевич	
"BUDJET JARAYONLARIDA XAVFLARNI ANIQLASH VA BAHOLASH: ICHKI AUDIT YONDASHUVLARI".....	941
Abdujalilova Dilnoz Abdusattorovna, Nishonxo'djaev Bekzod Baxodir o'g'li	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA DAVLATNING ROLI.....	947
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SUT SEKTORINING QIYMAT ZANJIRINI SANOATLASHTIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	951
Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBIDA XARAJATLAR HISOBI VA KALKULYATSIYA TIZIMLARINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	955
Namroyeva Zuhra Amiral qizi	
АНАЛИЗ И ОЦЕНКА ТЕКУЩЕГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНЕ.....	961
Ариф Мустафаев	
ФАКТОРЫ ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ДОХОДОВ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНОЧНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	968
Ишонкулова Феруза Асатовна	
O'ZBEKISTONNING INVESTITSION HUQUQIY SIYOSATIDA GLOBAL REYTINGLARNING NORMATIV-HUQUQIY ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	974
Gavhar Bekmurodova Adham qizi	
XALQARO MOLIYA BOZORIDA KREDIT RISKINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	981
Ochilova Xusniya Olim qizi, Yuldasheva Umida Asanaliyevna	
JAHONDA BRONLASH TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARINING EVOLYUTSIYASI.....	987
Ismatillaeva Sitara Sayfidin qizi	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOT INNOVATSION SALOHİYATIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHDA JAHON TAJRIBALARI.....	994
Samadqulov Muhammadjon Islom o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISHDA SOLIQ IMTIYOZLARINING AHOLI DAROMADLAR DINAMIKASIGA TA'SIRI.....	998
Olimjon Fattoyev G'ayrat o'g'li	
OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING ZAMONAVIY SHAROITLARDI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGI: NAZARIY JIHA TLARI VA AMALIY BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARI.....	1002
Adizov Bobir Baxtiyrovich	
ZAMONAVIY SHAROITDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RISKLARINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1005
Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin Ikromiddinovich, Nasritdinov Bekzod Xusnutdinovich	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA QURILISH KLASTERNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY OMILLARI VA ISTIQBOLLI MANBALARI.....	1011
Abduraxmanov Muxtorali Abduvoxi dovich	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	1016
Авезова Шахноза Махмуджановна	
MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIKNI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIR KO'RSATADIGAN OMILLAR.....	1022
Obilov Mirkomil Rashidovich	

“O‘ZBEKISTONDA TURIZMNING MADANIY IDENTIKLIKKA TA’SIRI: SOTSIOLOGIK TAHLIL”	1028
Alijonova Nargiza Rashidjon qizi	
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF CREDIT INTEREST RATES.....	1034
Abdullayev Shakhobiddin Shamsiddinovich	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA LOGISTIKA XARAJATLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH METODLARI VA SAMARALI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI MODELI.....	1037
Olimova Bahora Shuxratovna	
INNOVASION IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI.....	1042
Abdulkakimov Zuxrali Tursunaliyevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA DEPOZIT BAZASI BARQARORLIGIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMIL SIFATIDA FOIZ SIYOSATI VA UNING AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	1047
Axmedova Dilafro‘z Elshodovna	
B2BDA RAQAMLI MARKETINGDAN FOYDALANISH BO‘YICHA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR.....	1053
Abdubotirova Madinaxon	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ МЕХАНИЗМ ИННОВАЦИОННО - ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ОТРАСЛИ.....	1059
Баходирова Хилола Баходировна	
RAQOBATBARDOSH MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1063
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna, Abdurazakova Diyora	
ENERGIYA XARAJATLARINI KAMAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARASI.....	1070
Urmanbekova Iroda Farxodovna	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF REMOTE BANKING SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF BANKING TRANSFORMATION	1075
Jabborov Bahriddin Rashidovich	
MIKROMOLIYA TASHKILOTLARIDA MOLIYAVIY-XO‘JALIK FAOLIYATINI BUXGALTERIYA HISOBIDA AKS ETTIRISH TARTIBI.....	1079
G‘ofurov Iskandar Abduraxmonovich	
BANKLARNING INVESTITSIYA RISKLARI VA ULARNI KAMAYTIRISH YO‘LLARI	1084
Yuldashev Erkin Xusanovich	
MA‘LUMOTLAR BAZASINING RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	1090
Maxamadiyev M. M.	
УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ: АНАЛИЗ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ АКИБ «ИПОТЕКА-БАНК» ПОСЛЕ ВХОЖДЕНИЯ В OTP GROUP.....	1095
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
O‘ZBEKISTON OLIY TA‘LIM MUASSASALARIGA XORIJLIK TALABALARNI JALB ETISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1101
Sharopova Nafosat, Xolmamatov Diyorbek	
DAVLATNING IJOBIY IMIJINI YARATISHDA TURIZM VA XALQ DIPLOMATIYASINING STRATEGIK O‘RNI	1108
Kasimova Zilola G‘ulomiddin qizi	
JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORT MUASSASALARIDA MOLIYAVIY MUNOSABATLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	1116
Toshmurodov Abdurauf Ravshanovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПУТИ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ СИСТЕМЫ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ ТОПЛИВНО-ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОМПЛЕКСА УЗБЕКИСТАНА – 2025.....	1122
Ш.К.Жалилов	
“O‘ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING O‘RNI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI”	1126
Xursandov Komiljon Maxmatkulovich	
MAMLAKATDA INVESTITSIYA JARAYONLARINING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1130
Xusanov Durbek Nishanovich	
TURIZM XIZMATLARI TUSHUNCHASI VA ULARNI INNOVATSION TASHKIL ETISHNING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI.....	1138
Najmidinov Azizbek Bahrom o‘g‘li	

MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIYOTDA TURISTIK INFRATUZILMANI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA MEZONLARI.....	1143
<i>Xalmirzayev Axmadjan Axunovich, Ro'zmatov Boburjon Zafarjon o'g'li, Shodiyeva Nafosatxon Hamza qizi</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINING HOLATI VA TENDENSIYALARI.....	1149
<i>Ahmedov Shermuhammad Omonjon o'g'li</i>	
MARKETING KOMMUNIKATSIYA STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQUISHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	1156
<i>Akramov Toxir Abdiraxmanovich</i>	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	1161
<i>Adashev Azimjon Urinboyevich</i>	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA PRUDENSIAL NAZORAT: BAZEL QOIDALARI VA ULARNING AHAMIYATI	1165
<i>Abdunazarova Dilshoda Akromovna</i>	
INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI BOSHQARISHDA BOSHQARUV HISOBİ AXBOROTINING AHAMIYATI	1170
<i>Xushvaqtova Nozanin Nurbek qizi</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA INTEGRATSIYA JARAYONLARINI AMALGA OSHIRISH SHAKLLARI VA ULARNING TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	1177
<i>Ismoilova Feruza Kubaymurodovna</i>	
EKOMARKETING STRATEGIYALARI ORQALI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA ERISHISH	1182
<i>Qo'ziyev Jaloladdin Alisher o'g'li</i>	
ENSURING INNOVATIVE ECONOMIC SECURITY IN THE KHOREZM REGION: WASTE RECYCLING AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY	1186
<i>Mdraximova Shohista Bahrom qizi</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH ASOSIDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1191
<i>Mavrulov Ravshan Nematjonovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIGA ISLİM MOLIYASINI JORIY QILISHDA XORIYIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJIRIBASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1195
<i>Sultonov Baxtiyor Baxodirovich</i>	
MINTAQAVIY IMIJNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI.....	1201
<i>Duschanov Alisher Sherzod o'g'li</i>	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	1206
<i>Opaev Bysen Aymanovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNESNI INVESTITSION KREDITLARI ORQALI MOLIYALASHTIRISH.....	1212
<i>Yuldashev Fozil Turapovich</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI SAMARALI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XORIY TAJIRIBASI.....	1218
<i>M.M.Muminova</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИОННОЕ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЕ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНОГО ОПЕРАТОРА И ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ МЕСТНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ	1223
<i>Худаярова Мехрангиз Мурадовна</i>	
TURIZMDA INDIVIDUALLASHTIRILGAN XIZMATLAR KONSEPSIYASI VA TAJRIBA TURIZMINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	1230
<i>Raxmatov Aziz Tolipovich</i>	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK EKSTERNALIYALARNI TARTIBGA SOLISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1235
<i>Smaylova Zarafshan</i>	
XALQARO STANDARTLARDA PRUDENSIAL NAZORAT: BAZEL QOIDALARI VA ULARNING AHAMIYATI	1239
<i>Abdunazarov Dilshoda Akromovna</i>	

METALLURGIYA SANOATIDA EKOLOGIK TOZA TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH: MAQSADGA MUVOFIQLIGI VA NATIJALARI	1244
Karimov Ma'ruf Ixtiyorovich	
HUDDIY IQTISODIY O'SISH OMILLARINING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI: SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA	1248
Zaripova Mukaddas Djumayozovna, Normurodov Asliddin Alijon o'g'li	
INDUSTRIAL RIVOJLANISHNING IQTISODIY VA EKOLOGIK OQIBATLARI	1258
Ataniyazova M.B.	
OLIY TA'LIM RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHDAGI ROLI	1263
Nishonov Dilshod Shamsidinovich	
СИСТЕМА ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ЭЛЕМЕНТ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЕННОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	1269
Махмутходжаева Луиза Сайфуллоевна	
IQTISODIYOTDA "YASHIL" MOLIYALASHTIRISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XUSUSIYATLARI	1274
Risqibekova Nozimaxon	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN BOOSTING TOURISM-RELATED BUSINESSES	1280
Farrukh Mamadiyurov Shukhratovich	
MINTAQA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH INDIKATORLARI VA USLUBLARI	1284
Turdiyev Ulug'bek Qayumovich	
MAJOR INFLATIONARY FACTORS IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ANTI-INFLATION POLICIES	1290
Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli, Oralbaeva Diana Mukhit qizi	
ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОСИСТЕМА СОВРЕМЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА: МОДЕЛИ, МЕХАНИЗМЫ И НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ	1296
Бекова Азиза Алимовна	
SOLIQ MAJBURIYATLARINI HISOBGA OLISH JARAYONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	1301
Abdullayev Abror Bozarboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AKSIZ SOLIINING FISKAL VA IJTIMOYIY ROLI	1308
Abdulxayeva Shaxnoza Muxammadiyevna	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIYOTDA AGROTURIZMNI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA MEZONLARI	1314
Egamberdiyeva Umriniso Tursunqulovna, Ro'zmatov Boburjon Zafarjon o'g'li, Shodiyeva Nafosatxon Hamza qizi	
OLIY TA'LIMDAGI RAQAMLI YECHIMLARNING SAMARADORLIGI VA UNI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI	1320
Abduraxmanova Malika Abdujaparovna	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATI SHAROITIDA AKVAPARK VA SUZISH HAVZALARI QURILISHINI TAHLIL QILISH HAMDA TAVSIYALAR BERISH	1326
Olimjonov Firdavs	
FISKAL FEDERALIZM NAZARIYASI VA UNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI	1332
Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Alijonov Ahadjon Hasanboy o'g'li	
OILAVIY MUHITDA QIZLARNING EMOTSIONAL INTELLEKTINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: IJTIMOYIY PEDAGOGIK YONDASHUV (O'ZBEKISTONDA)	1336
Qayimova Maftuna Tursunovna	
«YASHIL IPOTEKA» AMALIYOTI: XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR	1340
Berdinazarov Zafar Ulashovich, Xayitov Bobirbek Ergashevich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ПРОЦЕССОВ ПРИНЯТИЯ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИХ РЕШЕНИЙ В ЭПОХУ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НОВОЙ ПАРАДИГМЫ КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ	1344
Бурханова Шахноза Бобировна	
QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATINI KENGAYTIRISH MASALALARI	1353
Abduvoxidova N.G., Karimova A.M.	
ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA ORQALI SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING ASOSIY MECHANIZMLARI	1359
Mirzarayimova Feruza Zokirjon qizi, Levakov Izzatulla Nematillayevich	

TO'G'RI SOLIQLARNI UNDIRISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH AMALIYOTI TAHLILI	1365
Xo'jaqulov Ramshid Yunusovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BANK TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	1372
Kasimova Zilolaxon Botir qizi	
INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MAZMUNI VA TAMOYILLARI	1379
Gafurov Ma'ruf Xakimovich	
KREDIT RISKI VA UNGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	1383
Karimova Shohida Zaylobiddinova	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATI TUMANLARINING IQTISODIY MODERNIZATSIYASI: ASOSIY OMILLAR VA TENDENSIYALAR.....	1389
Qosimova Nodira Saidovna	
BUXORO VILOYATIDA YASHIL AGROTURIZM KONSEPSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	1395
Umurov J.	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIDA DAROMADLAR VA ULARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	1403
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
MINTAQADA KICHIK BIZNESNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI.....	1409
Raxmatullayev Umarbek Ulug'bekovich	
FERMERLAR KOOPERATSIYASI VA XALQARO BOZORLARGA KIRISH: O'TISH DAVRI IQTISODIYOTIDAN XULQ-ATVOR, DEMOGRAFIK VA INSTITUTSIONAL NUQTAI NAZARLAR.....	1415
Tursunqulov G'olib Shavkat o'g'li	
ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNI KLASTER ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH	1422
Mamadiyev Elyor Akmalovich, Sharipov K. A.	
КОРПОРАТИВНОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ В АВТОМОБИЛЬНОМ СЕКТОРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: СТРАТЕГИИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РИСКАМИ ДЛЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РОСТА И СОБЛЮДЕНИЯ РЕГУЛЯТОРНЫХ ТРЕБОВАНИЙ	1427
Шамсуддинов Шухрат Нематович	
ПУТИ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ И СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА НА ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ.....	1431
U. D. Gayratov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOM MOLIYASIGA BO'LGAN EHTIYOJ VA ZARURIYAT: UNING AHAMIYATI.....	1435
Sh.N.G'afforov	
MEHNAT RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH VA UNI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI	1439
Uzoqov Lutfillon Fayzullojonovich	
DAVLAT TOMONIDAN IQTISODIY NAZORATNING BOZOR BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDAGI ROLI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI VA GLOBAL AMALIYOT TAHLILI	1443
Rasulev Alisher Fayziyevich. Karimov Ulug'bek Mirzajon o'g'li	
TASHQI DAVLAT QARZINING VALYUTA TUZILMASI VA UNING QARZ BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRI TAHLILI	1446
Sanakulova B. R., Jamolov M.M.	
ASOSIY MAKROIQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLAR ORQALI DAROMADLAR O'SISHINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI.....	1452
Eshbaeva Shahnoza Faxriddinova	
ЭКОНОМИКА УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И ПРАКТИКА.....	1457
Рустамов Зокир Тоирович	
EKSPORT DIVERSIFIKATSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA AKT NING ROLI: RIVOJLANAYOTGAN DAVLATLAR MISOLIDA	1461
Sadriddinov Ulug'bek Jaloliddin o'g'li	
ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫМИ ПОТОКАМИ И ИМПОРТОМ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	1467
Рустамов Фозилжон	
ICHKI BOZORDA PARRANDA GO'SHTI MAHSULOTINING NARX BARQARORLIGI VA KELGUSI TENDENSIYALARINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLAR ORQALI BAHOLASH	1475
Jumayev Olimjon Sadulloevich	

TIBBIY XIZMAT INFRATUZILMASINING FARG'ONA IQTISODIY RAYONIDA JOYLASHUV XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1483
<i>Xolmirzayeva Zulayxo Axmadjon qizi</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH BO'YICHA METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR ISHLAB CHIQUISH.....	1488
<i>Ibragimova Shaxlo Alimbayevna</i>	
ENERGY TRANSITION DEBATE: ELECTRIC VEHICLES, OIL AND THE "GREEN" PARADOX.....	1492
<i>Tokhirjonov Temurbek Alimardon ogli, Numonjon Malikov</i>	
SANOATLASHUV NATIJASIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINING KAMAYISHI TAHLILI	1500
<i>B.Beknazarov</i>	
RESPUBLIKA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINING SHAKLLANISHI VA MUSTAQILLIK YILLARIDA RIVOJLANISHI.....	1505
<i>Nurboyev Jaloliddin Mamadiyevich</i>	
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" VA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYANING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	1510
<i>Qurbonov Shovqi Djurayevich</i>	
THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS IN THE COURSE OF ACUTE RHEUMATIC FEVER IN CHILDREN	1516
<i>Kuldashev Sardor Furqatovich</i>	
MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYA DARAJASINI BAHOLASHNING AXBOROT TIZIMI ASOSIDA MONITORING MEXANIZMLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	1520
<i>Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o'g'li</i>	
EKSPORT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INNOVATSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI	1527
<i>Sobirova Muxlisa</i>	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLAR MUSTAQILLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQ TUSHUMLARI VA TRANSFERTLAR NISBATINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	1531
<i>Muxitdinov Sidikxo'ja Akobirxo'ja o'g'li</i>	
BANK TIZIMI ORQALI YASHIL MOLIYANI RIVOJLANTIRISH: GREEN ADVISORY SERVICES XIZMATLARINING ZAMONAVIY AMALIYOTI.....	1537
<i>Abdumutalova Gulrux Shuxratjon qizi</i>	
ISLOMIY MOLIYA VA RAQAMLI BANK EKOTIZIMLARINING INTEGRATSIYASINING O'ZBEKISTONDAGI ISTIQBOLLARI	1544
<i>Galatov Abbos Alibekovich</i>	
AGROSERVIS XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	1551
<i>Abilov Feruz Nematullayevich</i>	
TRANSFORMATSIYALASH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI KREDITLARI AMALIYOTI BILAN BOG'LIQ MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI	1554
<i>Jabbarov Nodir Umirovich</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM MALAKALARINI XALQARO TAN OLIHNING INSTITUTSIONAL MEXANIZMLARI: BOLONYA JARAYONI VA YUNESKO GLOBAL KONVENSIYASI QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	1559
<i>Saidov Muxammad Ali Hakimovich, Iminoxunov Abduqahhor Abduvohidovich</i>	
IQTISODIY O'SISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNI BELGILOVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	1563
<i>G'ulomjan Matkarimov</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MUZEY TURIZMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL YO'NALISHLARI.....	1568
<i>Yulduz Urinbayeva</i>	
DEVELOPMENT OF A METHODOLOGY FOR THE DIGITALIZATION OF TANGIBLE TECHNICAL ASSET INVENTORY IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	1573
<i>Izzatilla Pulatov Quدراتillayevich</i>	
THE IMPACT OF NATIONAL ECONOMY COMPETITIVENESS ON ECONOMIC GROWTH	1581
<i>Siddikov Askar Axrorovich, Turapov Siroj Mamadoli o'g'li</i>	

TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN AGRAR SEKTORNI MOLIALASHTIRISH TIZIMI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NASHISHLARI	1585
Azizov Shuxrat Maxmutovich	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINI O'QITISHGA QARATILGAN LOYIHALARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIK TAHLILI.....	1593
Rapiyev Alisher Parda o'g'li, Toshboyev Ikrom O'ktamovich	
MINTAQALARNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TADBIRKORLIK SALOHİYATI AHAMIYATINING ILMIY-NAZARIY JIHATLARI	1597
Madaminov Damir Abduraxmanovich	
АБСОРБЦИОННАЯ СПОСОБНОСТЬ И ПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ТРУДА: МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ МЕЖСТРАНОВОГО АНАЛИЗА	1602
Султанова Л.Ш.	
KADRLAR MENEJMENTIDA MOTIVATSIYA TIZIMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	1607
Latipov Ashur Ali Rustam o'g'li, Xakimov Damir Ulug'bekovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHI VA MILLIY IQTISODIY STRATEGIYAGA TA'SIRI.....	1612
Artikova Shoxida Ilyasovna, Xakimov Damir Ulug'bekovich	
“YASHIL” IQTISODIYOT TAMOIYILLARI ASOSIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI.....	1616
Rustamov Narzillo Istamovich	
KATTA HAJMDAGI MA'LUMOTLAR (BIG DATA) ORQALI EKOLOGIK VA IQTISODIY JARAYONLARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	1621
Mullajonova Fotima Tuychibayevna	
ТОРГОВЫЙ БАЛАНС МЕЖДУ УЗБЕКИСТАНОМ И КИТАЕМ И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ЭКОНОМИКУ: АНАЛИЗ ОТРАСЛЕЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ	1627
He Xiaocu, Уркинбаев Т. А.	
РЕЙТИНГОВАЯ ОЦЕНКА ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ АСПЕКТОВ ДЛЯ ДАЛЬНЕЙШЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ «ЗЕЛЕННОЙ» ЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	1632
Тураева Сурия	
HUDUDLARNI IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ERKIN IQTISODIY HUDUDLARNING O'RNI	1641
N. Tursunov	
ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГА В B2B- И B2C-СЕКТОРАХ ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ.....	1646
Садий Шукрилло Асатилло угли	
ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ВНЕШНЕЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ В ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ	1653
Qian Xuanhong, Вохидова Мехри	
MAHALLALARDA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH — KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISHNING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	1659
Xolmuratov Salimbek Eshbekovich	
DAVLAT QARZLARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	1663
Valiyeva Gulxayyo, Samandarova Gulmira	
YASHIL TURIZMNING MOHIYATI VA UNI TASHKIL ETISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	1666
Qurbanbayev Shuhrat Bakberganovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI SHAROITIDA ISLOM BANKLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	1670
S. Sayfullayev	
IT LOYIHALARINI BOSHQARISHNING TASHKILY JIHATLARI	1675
Mansurova Bibinur Miyirbek Qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONNING INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	1679
Babaeva Nargiza Muzafarovna	
KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH DASTURLARINI BAJARILISHIDA MOLIVAVIY SIYOSAT DOIRASIDA MOLIVAVIY DASTAKLARDAN FOYDALANISHDAGI TENDENSIYALAR TAHLILI.....	1686
Mirzaxalikov Bobir Baxtiyorovich	

KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARI FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	1692
Mullajanov Iskandar Tadjibayevich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA MARKETING KOMMUNIKATSIYALARI VA KONTENT MARKETINGNING O'RNI	1697
Bozorov Samar Safarovich	
JANUBIY KOREYADA TIBBIY TURIZMNING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH TAJRIBASI	1702
Azizova Nazira To'xtayevna	
MINTAQADA EKOLOGIK XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI TAHLILI	1708
Odilov Xamidillo Maxmudjon o'g'li	
"IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENSURING RESOURCE ECONOMY IN THE FIELD OF COTTON GROWING IN THE AGRARIAN SECTOR.....	1715
Mirzaev Batir, Djumabaeva Nurzada Torebekovna	
TRANSCHEGARAVIY ELEKTRON TIJORATDA BOJXONA TO'LOVLARI HISOBI VA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING AYRIM MASALALARI.....	1719
Makkamov Zokirjon Xusanboyevich	
TO'SIQSIZ TURIZMNING XUSUSIYATLARI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI.....	1723
Umurzakova D. E.	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО МЕХАНИЗМА РАЗВИТИЯ МИСЕ-ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	1729
Нарзуллаева Фариза Акмалевна	
MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK TARMOG'I – MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNING ASOSIY BO'G'INI SIFATIDA.....	1734
Israilova Xikoyat Musakulovna	
DAVR XARAJATLARI HISOBI VA TAHLILI	1739
Sh.M. Ergashev	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	1744
Nosirov Sardor Xolmirzayevich	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL CURRENCY IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENT.....	1750
Malikov Numonjon Kamalovich, Azimov Khumoyun Khamid ugli, Pardayev Khusniddin Jakhongir ugli	

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL CURRENCY IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENT

**Malikov Numonjon
Kamalovich**

UWED, Senior Lecturer,
Department of International
Finance and Investments
nmalikov@uwed.uz
ORCID: 0000-0002-0172-0195

**Azimov Khumoyun
Khamid ugli**

UWED, Master's Student,
Foreign Economic Activity
khamidovich02@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0009-8143-
2377

**Pardayev Xhusniddin
Jakhongir ugli**

UWED, Master's Student,
Foreign Economic Activity
xusniddinpardayev710@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0007-2257-2105

Abstract. In the context of the digital transformation of the global financial system, digital currencies are emerging as a significant instrument reshaping investment processes. The increasing adoption of digital currencies, including central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) and stablecoins, by central banks and private financial institutions influences cross-border capital flows, national investment attractiveness, and investor confidence. The purpose of this article is to analyze the role of digital currencies in attracting investments and to identify the key mechanisms through which they affect investment decisions. The study examines the theoretical foundations of digital currencies, analyzes international case studies of CBDC implementation and crypto-asset usage, and evaluates regulatory and macroeconomic factors that determine the effectiveness of digital currencies as an investment promotion tool. Particular attention is paid to the reduction of transaction costs, increased transparency of financial operations, and enhanced financial inclusion. The findings suggest that digital currencies can contribute to investment attraction provided that a stable regulatory framework, effective supervision, and macroeconomic stability are ensured.

Key words: digital currency, investment, CBDC, stablecoins, financial technologies, investment attractiveness.

Annotatsiya. Jahon moliya tizimining raqamlashtirilishi sharoitida raqamli valyutalar investitsiya jarayonlarini transformatsiya qilishda muhim vositaga aylanmoqda. Markaziy banklar va xususiy moliya institutlari tomonidan raqamli valyutalar, jumladan markaziy bank raqamli valyutalari (CBDC) va stejblkoinlarning joriy etilishi kapitalning transchegaraviy harakati, mamlakatlarning investitsiyaviy jozibadorligi hamda investorlar ishonchiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi raqamli valyutalarning investitsiyalarni jalb etishdagi rolini tahlil qilish hamda ularning investitsion qarorlarga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy mexanizmlarini aniqlashdan iborat. Maqolada raqamli valyutalarning nazariy asoslari ko'rib chiqilib, CBDC joriy etilishi bo'yicha xalqaro tajribalar va kriptoaktivlardan foydalanish amaliyoti tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, raqamli valyutalarning investitsiyalarni rag'batlantirishdagi samaradorligini belgilovchi tartibga soluvchi va makroiqtisodiy omillar baholanadi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, raqamli valyutalar mustahkam huquqiy baza, samarali nazorat mexanizmlari va makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik mavjud bo'lgan sharoitda investitsiyalarni jalb etishga xizmat.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli valyuta, investitsiya, markaziy bank raqamli valyutasi, stejblkoinlar, moliyaviy texnologiyalar, investitsion jozibadorlik.

Аннотация. В условиях цифровизации мировой финансовой системы цифровые валюты становятся одним из ключевых инструментов трансформации инвестиционных процессов. Центральные банки и частные финансовые институты активно внедряют цифровые валюты, включая цифровые валюты центральных банков (CBDC) и

стейблкоины, что оказывает влияние на трансграничные потоки капитала, инвестиционную привлекательность государств и уровень доверия со стороны инвесторов. Цель данной статьи заключается в анализе роли цифровых валют в привлечении инвестиций, а также в выявлении основных механизмов их воздействия на инвестиционные решения. В статье рассматриваются теоретические основы цифровых валют, анализируются международные кейсы внедрения CBDC и использования крипто активов, а также оцениваются регуляторные и макроэкономические факторы, определяющие эффективность цифровых валют как инструмента инвестиционного стимулирования. Особое внимание уделяется вопросам снижения транзакционных издержек, повышения прозрачности финансовых операций и расширения финансовой доступности. В результате исследования делается вывод о том, что цифровые валюты могут способствовать привлечению инвестиций при условии наличия устойчивой нормативно-правовой базы, эффективного надзора и макроэкономической стабильности.

Ключевые слова: цифровая валюта, инвестиции, CBDC (цифровая валюта центрального банка), стейблкоины, финансовые технологии, инвестиционная привлекательность.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most obvious signs of technological progress in the last few decades has been the way people, society, and the state deal with money. The rise of digital assets, especially digital currency, which is a new way to make, save, and spend money, is what caused this.

The most recent reports say that more than \$250 million worth of digital financial assets were issued between September 2022 and July 2023. By 2030, the total value of all the digital financial assets that have been issued will be more than \$60 billion. Some countries have also officially launched central bank digital currencies (Pic. 1). These are Nigeria, the Bahamas, and Jamaica. There will be 15 of them by 2030. The IMF says that seven countries, including Russia, India, Kazakhstan, and China, are now in the fourth pilot stage of developing CBDC. The People's Bank of China (NBK) has done the best. It began looking into the Central Securities Market in 2014, and the first prototype was released in 2016. It was also decided that the digital yuan (e-CNY) should be made and released at some point in the future. As part of a pilot program, almost 20 million Chinese stores accepted digital yuan by March 2023. There were more than 750 million e-CNY transactions in 17 provinces and municipalities of the People's Republic of China, totaling 900 billion yuan [1].

CBDC could have a big effect on global finance by changing how payments are made, how financial intermediaries work, and how monetary policy is put into action. Because the economy is going digital so quickly and capital is moving across borders more often, it is becoming more important to study what might happen if central securities are put in place. "Digital currency" is a new idea, but it is already a big part of the market that is growing quickly all over the world. So, we think that the authorities need to look at the history of this phenomenon and explain its theoretical basis in order to effectively regulate the digital currencies market and keep the information safe for all the people who use it.

Digital currencies are beginning to be regarded as more than mere payment methods; they are increasingly perceived as factors influencing investment levels and the attractiveness of countries to investors. The rules and policies set by the government and other organizations have a big effect on how quickly investment processes grow in the digital economy. The state is important for making sure that the investment climate is good, that new financial products like digital currencies are safe, and that the rules for investments are clear. To understand how digital currencies can get people to invest, we need to look at their economic value, investment potential, and the ways that governments control them.

PIC 1. Status of CBDC in countries according to year 2025

This article seeks to analyze the impact of CBDC on the global financial system, outline possible advantages and disadvantages, and investigate the future evolution of this technology. And mostly about how it affects getting investments

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent studies emphasize that digital currencies have become an important factor influencing global investment flows in the context of financial digitalization. Research highlights that the adoption of digital currencies reduces transaction costs, increases payment efficiency, and enhances transparency in financial markets, thereby improving the overall investment climate [1]. These characteristics are particularly relevant for attracting foreign direct investment in emerging and developing economies.

A growing body of literature focuses on central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) as a tool for strengthening financial stability and investor confidence. Empirical findings suggest that CBDCs can improve monetary policy transmission, reduce settlement risks, and facilitate cross-border capital movements, which positively affect long-term investment attractiveness [2]. Studies also note that countries with clear CBDC strategies tend to signal institutional reliability to international investors.

In parallel, research on stablecoins indicates that their price stability and blockchain-based infrastructure support efficient capital allocation and lower exchange rate risks for investors [3]. Stablecoins are increasingly viewed as intermediate instruments that bridge traditional finance and decentralized financial systems, making them attractive for portfolio diversification and international investment transactions.

Several analyses underline the importance of regulatory frameworks in determining the investment impact of digital currencies. Well-designed legal and supervisory mechanisms are found to mitigate risks related to volatility, money laundering, and cybersecurity, thereby fostering investor trust [4]. Conversely, regulatory uncertainty is shown to limit the positive investment effects of digital currency adoption.

Finally, macroeconomic-oriented studies argue that the investment benefits of digital currencies depend on broader economic conditions, including financial infrastructure, digital literacy, and institutional quality [5]. Digital currencies are most effective in attracting investment when integrated into a stable macroeconomic environment supported by sound financial governance and technological readiness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applies a descriptive and analytical approach to examine the role of digital currencies in attracting investment. The analysis is based on a review of international reports, regulatory documents, and recent empirical studies related to digital currencies, including central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) and stablecoins. Comparative analysis is used to assess differences in investment dynamics across countries with varying levels of digital currency adoption. The study also evaluates regulatory and macroeconomic factors influencing the effectiveness of digital currencies in supporting investment decisions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Digital assets are things that have value or stand for rights that are made, stored, and moved around online. These kinds of assets can be digital on their own or digital versions of physical assets. The most important questions were how similar the ideas of “digital assets,” “crypto assets,” and “digital currencies” are and what standards they can be grouped by. This study has shown that these asset categories are not only linked to each other, but they also have an effect on each other in terms of function, institutions, and the economy.

Some digital assets are not crypto assets. For example, some digital assets are not made with new technologies like blockchains, distributed ledgers, smart contracts, and so on.

But crypto assets are one of the most common and important kinds of digital assets. Digital currencies and digital assets may also be the same thing. The latter is true because some crypto assets, like cryptocurrencies and stablecoins, can be traded and used as investments or settlement assets on the crypto market. They can also do some or all of the things that money does in the traditional economy, such as being a way to save, a way to pay, or a way to keep track of things. Also, transactions that involve digital assets.

It is possible to do transactions in digital currencies on a platform basis by bringing together the rules for issuing, validating, cryptographic, and software standards and automating the execution of transactions through smart contracts.

The central bank’s digital currency is the third type of fiat currency, after cash and non-cash. Fiat currency is money that only exists in electronic form. Researchers and professionals in the field of finance have been paying more and more attention to it in recent years. The blockchain and cryptography technologies that power digital assets like Bitcoin, Ethereum, and central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) are changing the

way traditional financial systems work in a big way. The use of digital currencies in finance affects the global economy in many ways, such as how payments are made, how money is transferred, and how monetary policy is set. These changes are already having a big effect on the current financial system, making things easier and harder for global markets and regulators. At the same time, the main thing that separates digital currencies into two big groups is the subject of issue and control. Based on their unique traits, digital currencies can be split into centralised or decentralised groups, and then into other groups. The two main directions of digital currency development that were talked about above show that this criterion is correct. Figure 2 shows a schematic of how digital currencies are grouped.

Pic 2. Classification of Digital Currencies by Issuer and Control Entity

How CBDC affects investments through payment systems and cross-border settlements

One way that central banks' digital currencies (CBDCs) affect investment activity is by modernising payment systems and lowering transaction costs. In traditional financial systems, especially when money is

sent across borders, a lot of middlemen are needed to move money, which takes a long time and costs a lot of money. This makes operations more expensive and less efficient at moving capital around, which makes the markets less attractive for investors. CBDCs are a digital version of central bank money that lets people in the payment system settle directly with each other. This cuts down on transaction costs and speeds up financial transactions.

Pic 3. The Roles of CBDC in the Payment Market [5]

CBDC's role as a payment platform is very important for competition because it sets the rules for the different economic incentives along the value chain. The rules for the CBDC platform, such as the fees that will be charged and which intermediaries will be able to access the platform and under what conditions they will be able to do so, will have an effect on current pricing structures, business models, and the number of people who can take part in the CBDC ecosystem. A CBDC platform can encourage more competition, lower prices charged by dominant players directly or indirectly, and a more even distribution of value across the system by setting clear and fair rules. CBDC could help fix problems in the payments chain at different levels. For example, it could make competition better at the platform layer by giving people a competing payment platform or at the intermediary layer by making a platform that encourages better competition among intermediaries by making it easier for them to access, requiring interoperability, and setting technological standards, like standardised quick response (QR) codes for payments. With compatible national and regional CBDC platforms, settlements can be carried out in near real time, which reduces currency spreads, reduces the need for correspondent accounts, and increases transparency of transactions. For investors, this means more predictable cash flows, faster capital turnover, and a reduced need for complex mechanisms to hedge currency risks. This effect is especially significant for cross-border investments, where the cost and speed of settlements directly affect the profitability of investment projects [6].

Central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) have a competitive effect on investments through a number of channels that change both the price parameters and the way people participate in the payment market. Four channels through which CBDC affects competition in payment systems are found as part of the analytical approach. The first two channels, price and value, show that there are very competitive margins and are linked to changes in fees, transaction costs, and the quality of payment services. The other two channels—competitiveness and financial access—show that there are wide competition margins, which are caused by intermediaries entering and leaving the market, as well as end users getting involved. These channels show how CBDCs can change the way the payment market works by lowering costs, making things more efficient, increasing competition, and making it easier for everyone to get credit.

So, we looked at what digital currency is and how it can change investments. Sadly, we can't give real numbers right now because almost all of the projects are still in pilot mode, except for three. These three countries have also launched projects relatively recently, which complicates the analysis stage. For example, Nigeria, from launch to December 2021, over 600,000 eNaira wallets have been created and more than thirty-five thousand transactions have taken place. Currently, 90 percent of transactions are between people and businesses. Based on the level of identity provided, a higher transaction limit for the eNaira is allowed. With a phone number and verified national identity, users can make payments of up to 50,000 Naira (\$121) a day, rising to 200,000 (\$484) for the lower level of bank-approved account.

Pic 4. Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$) – Nigeria

Source: World Databank Group [7]

Despite the launch of the central bank's digital currency in 2021, the dynamics of foreign direct investment in subsequent years has shown a steadily negative trend. In 2021, the volume of foreign direct investment amounted to 3.31 billion US dollars, but in 2022, net capital outflow was recorded at the level of -186.8 million US dollars. The decline continued further: in 2023, the inflow of investments decreased to 1.87 billion US dollars, and in 2024 — to 1.08 billion US dollars. The goals of the eNaira are to improve financial inclusion, improve the accountability of the informal sector, and facilitate remittances. The eNaira is expected to help Nigeria reach its target of increasing financial inclusion from 64 percent to 95 percent. It is projected that a well-managed eNaira could add twenty-nine billion dollars to the GDP over the next ten years.

Pic 5. Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$) - Bahamas, The, Jamaica [8]

Situation with other two countries look not different. The graph shows that since 2020, when the central bank's digital currency projects (Jam-Dex and Sand Dollar) were launched in Jamaica and the Bahamas, the flow of foreign direct investment has not shown any long-term positive structural changes. In Jamaica, there was a brief recovery in 2021–2022, but then there were unstable changes and a drop in FDI inflows. This shows that the introduction of CBDCs does not have a long-term effect on investment. The same thing is happening in the Bahamas: after 2020, the amount of foreign direct investment stays in a narrow range without a clear upward trend.

These indicators indicate that the introduction of digital currency alone did not lead to an increase in investment activity and did not ensure a steady inflow of capital. The current situation confirms that the central bank's digital currency is not an independent and automatic factor in attracting foreign direct investment. Its impact on investment processes is indirect and is realized through improving the payment infrastructure, reducing transaction costs and increasing the transparency of financial transactions. In the absence of accompanying institutional reforms, a stable macroeconomic environment, and investor confidence, the potential benefits of digital currency are insufficient to offset the negative effects of external and internal factors, which limits its impact on the investment attractiveness of the economy [9].

Risks of CBDC implementation and their impact on investment decisions

Despite the potential advantages of introducing digital currencies of central banks, this process may be accompanied by risks of bank disintermediation associated with the redistribution of funds of economic agents from commercial bank deposits to the central bank's digital money, especially in the absence of restrictions on the storage volume of CBDCs or with the high attractiveness of this instrument compared to banking products, which can reduce the resource base of the bank to limit its ability to lend to the real sector of the economy and, as a result, This can lead to an increase in the cost of borrowed capital and a decrease in investment activity, primarily in projects focused on bank financing [10].

An additional risk factor in the introduction of digital currencies by central banks is institutional and regulatory uncertainty, covering issues of the legal status of digital money, the protection of personal data and confidentiality of transactions, the distribution of rights and obligations between participants in the payment system, as well as compliance with anti-money laundering and terrorist financing requirements. At the same time, the lack of a clear and predictable regulatory framework can increase the perception of country and regulatory risk by institutional and long-term investors, which negatively affects investment expectations and decisions, while analytical studies by central banks, including the European Central Bank, indicate that specific CBDC design parameters such as the interest-bearing or non-interest-bearing nature of the instrument setting limits on balances and AML/KYC architecture — They are of direct importance for maintaining financial stability and building investor confidence in the national financial system [11].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis shows that digital currencies of central banks represent an important element of the transformation of the modern financial system, but their impact on the investment attractiveness of the economy is not automatic or universal. By itself, the introduction of a CBDC does not guarantee an increase in capital inflows, since investment decisions are shaped by a wide range of factors, including macroeconomic stability, the quality of institutions, the level of development of financial markets and the predictability of government policy. The research indicates that central bank digital currencies alone do not enhance a country's appeal to investors. Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs) have the potential to modernise the financial system; nevertheless, their beneficial impact on investment is contingent upon the implementation of additional measures. These measures encompass the development of a broader array of financial instruments, including green bonds, funds, and green credit facilities; enhancing the institutional frameworks governing sustainable finance; elevating public awareness and engagement in green financing; and augmenting international collaboration with foreign investors and development partners. Digital financial advances can only facilitate sustainable investment development within a comprehensive economic and institutional framework [12].

With a well-thought-out approach, CBDCs and related digital initiatives can contribute to improving the efficiency of the payment infrastructure, reducing transaction costs and speeding up financial settlements, including in a cross-border format. These changes create more favorable conditions for capital flows, expand access to financial services, and encourage the involvement of a wider range of economic agents in investment processes. In the long term, this can support the development of domestic sources of investment, stimulate innovative financial instruments, and strengthen the integration of national economies into global financial and trade chains.

However, the potential benefits of CBDC implementation are closely related to the quality of their design and institutional support. Insufficiently developed solutions in the field of regulation, data protection,

risk management and interaction with the banking sector can create additional sources of uncertainty and undermine investor confidence. In such circumstances, possible negative effects, including financial instability or weakening of credit intermediation, can offset the positive impact of digital currencies on investment activity.

In this regard, an effective CBDC policy should be based on a phased implementation based on pilot projects and an ongoing assessment of their economic impacts. Transparency of regulatory decisions, open dialogue with financial institutions and investors, as well as international cooperation aimed at harmonizing standards and improving the compatibility of payment systems are essential. This approach allows us to consider the digital currencies of central banks as a long-term development tool, the potential of which is realized only with the presence of stable institutions and consistent economic policies.

REFERENCES

1. Solovyeva, O. V., & Nam, M. V. (2025). Digital Currencies: From the First Attempts to Create Alternative Value to Classification by Type and Features. *Accounting Analysis Auditing*, 12(5), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.26794/2408-9303-2025-12-5-22-32>
2. Atlantic Council. CBDC Tracker [Electronic resource] // Atlantic Council. 2025. URL: <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/cbdctracker/> (accessed: 16.12.2025).
3. Dmitry Kochergin, & Sergey Andryushin. (2023). Digital assets, crypto-assets and digital currencies: Economic content and potential of convergence. *Вестник Санкт-Петербургского университета*, 39(4), 496–533. <https://doi.org/10.21638/spbu05.2023.403>
4. Lyubov, Z. V. (2024). Роль цифровой валюты в развитии мировой финансовой системы. *Voenvestnik.ru*. <https://voenvestnik.ru/28es1224.html>
5. Edona . (2025, November 13). The Impact of Central Bank Digital Currency on Payments Competition. IMF. <https://www.imf.org/en/publications/fintech-notes/issues/2025/11/11/the-impact-of-central-bank-digital-currency-on-payments-competition-571638>
6. RESLOW, A., SODERBERG, G., & TSUDA, N. (2024, May 15). Cross-Border Payments with Retail Central Bank Digital Currencies. IMF. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fintech-notes/Issues/2024/05/15/Cross-Border-Payments-with-Retail-Central-Bank-Digital-Currencies-547195>
7. World Bank. (2023). Foreign Direct investment, Net Inflows (BoP, Current US\$) - Nigeria|Data. *Data.worldbank.org*. URL: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BX.KLT.DINV.CD.WD?locations=NG>
8. World Bank. (2023). Foreign Direct investment, Net Inflows (BoP, Current US\$) - Bahamas, The, Jamaica|Data. *Data.worldbank.org*. URL: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BX.KLT.DINV.CD.WD?locations=BS-JM>
9. Malikov, N. (2023). The Importance of Attracting Quality Investments. *International Affairs*, (3-4). <https://international-affairs.uz/storage/01JHG6SCK1GND3B5SN0VMFYZ9K.pdf>
10. Bouis, R. (2024, October 11). Central Bank Digital Currencies and Financial Stability: Balance Sheet Analysis and Policy Choices. IMF. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2024/10/11/Central-Bank-Digital-Currencies-and-Financial-Stability-Balance-Sheet-Analysis-and-Policy-556246>
11. Dionysopoulos, L., Marra, M., & Urquhart, A. (2023). Central bank digital currencies: A critical review. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 91(91), 103031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2023.103031>
12. Nu'monjon Malikov. (2024). O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga sarmoya kiritishning hozirgi holati va istiqbollari: barqaror rivojlanish sari. *GREEN ECONOMY and DEVELOPMENT*, 2(9). <https://www.yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/journal/index.php/GED/article/view/2988>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 12

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>